

EVALUATION OF THE RESEARCH PROTOCOL: *“Human Robot Adaptive Collaboration – HRAC”*- prot. *HRAC_Code_2023_31*

APPLICANT: Dr. Matteo Manzardo

Dear Researcher,

With reference to your request for approval of the research protocol: *“Human Robot Adaptive Collaboration – HRAC”* and the amendments you made following the recommendation of the Ethics Committee held on 20 December 2023, we inform you that the Research Ethics Committee has approved your research protocol *“Human Robot Adaptive Collaboration – HRAC”*.

Bolzano, 27 February 2024

The Research Ethics Committee of the Free University of Bolzano

Request for approval of a research protocol

This form collects all required information for Ethical scrutiny, **including** attachments. Please do not change the numbering of sections and attachments. For each section indicate which attachments will be included, removing references to unused attachments. **Send the form in a single digitally signed pdf file and the correspondent word file, by e-mail with subject "Request for Research Ethics Committee Approval" to: researchethics@unibz.it**

Legend: in cross questions (e.g. " **YES** **NO**"), the selected answer is the one marked as follows: (e.g. " **YES** **NO**", 'NO' is selected).

SECTION 1 –PRESENTATION OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT

1.1 Title

HUMAN ROBOT ADAPTIVE COLLABORATION

1.1.2 Acronym

HRAC

1.2 Principal Investigator:

Name and Surname	Renato Vidoni
Role/Position in UNIBZ	Full Professor
Department	Faculty of Engineering
E-mail	renato.vidoni@unibz.it
Phone Number	+39 333 5067093

- **Attachment 1.2.1:** please attach your CV (Concise and focused; max. 2 pages)

1.3 Other researcher(s) involved: please list all the people who will participate in the research and have access to the raw data.

Name and Surname	Luca Gualtieri
Affiliation (please indicate the name of the relevant institute)	Free University of Bolzano
Role/Position	RTDb
Role in the Project	Investigator

Name and Surname	Matteo Manzardo
Affiliation (please indicate the name of the relevant institute)	Free University of Bolzano
Role/Position	PhD Student
Role in the Project	Investigator

- **Attachment 1.3 (a, b, c...):** please attach a concise and focused CVs of people involved in the project (max. 1 page with no more than 5 publications significant to the project).

1.4 Location where research is conducted: Smart Mini Factory Lab / FiRST Lab

1.5 Are the opinions of other ethics committees and/or approvals from other entities (e.g., hospitals, schools, prisons) required for data access or participant involvement?

YES NO

If YES, please attach copy of the request for opinion/authorization. ¹

.....
.....

- **Attachment 1.5:** copy of the positive opinion issued by other Ethics Committees and/or authorization obtained from involved Institutions. In the absence of these, attach a copy of the submitted application.

1.6 Indicate any Funding Entities/Sponsors, the extent of their contributions and special agreements made.

The activity is carried out within the European project SESTOSENSO (Grant Agreement 101070310). The research is conducted by Unibz's researchers and they will be the only people allowed to manage raw data. The University of Bologna will borrow an EDA (Electro Dermal Activity) and an Heart Rate Measurement instrument. However, they will be operated only by Unibz's employees.

1.7 Do the person(s) in charge and members of the research team as well as their respective family members have potential conflicts of interest in relation to the conduct and outcome of the study?

YES NO

If yes, please specify:

.....
.....

1.8 Are there any interventions that require specific professional skills (e.g., medical consultants, psychologists/psychologists, nurses, etc.) under current regulations?

YES NO

¹ If already obtained opinion from other EU Ethics Committee that also covers the UNIBZ researcher's research, one can previously send the application and the already obtained opinion to the ERC, which will evaluate it and possibly can validate it. In this case it is not necessary to fill out this application. It is necessary that the documents be in Italian, German or English.

If YES, please specify how these professional profiles are involved in the project (name and surname of the professional, professional registration).

.....

SECTION 2 – PROJECT DETAILS

2.1 Expected start date of the research ² 27/12/2023

2.2 Expected duration of the research (in months) 4 months

2.3 Summary of the research program

(objective procedure - max 500 words):

The project has the goal to investigate human-robot interaction within working context.

The participants will be asked to perform tasks with a collaborative robot (industrial robot that can safely operate alongside humans in a shared workspace).

The proposed method allows humans to regulate the robot's speed by utilizing data derived from the point where they are looking, known as the eye's gaze point. The method is based on the following assumption: when the operator is observing the robot / has the robot in its field of view, he/she is generally more aware of the robot's actions with respect to the moments in which the robot is out of the field of view of the operator. The developed method increases the speed of the robot, within a maximum limit speed, as the attention of the operator increases (e.g. when the observation point of the human gets closer to the robot).

The overall purpose of the project is to understand how well the human-robot collaboration works in terms of efficiency and quality of the collaboration and whether the proposed method of adjusting robot speed based on the operator's attention is effective.

2.4 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT:

2.4.1 Background and theoretical justification (literature review - max 500 words)

Nowadays, collaborative robots are gaining more and more importance in industrial environments, thanks to their capabilities of physically interacting with humans in a shared workspace. In the development of a collaborative workstation, it is important to consider both the mechanical and the psychological [1] safety/risks associated with such workstations. With respect to mechanical risks, the ISO/TS 15066 technical specification defines the conditions under which a manipulator can operate when interacting with the human. With respect to psychological risks associated to such operations, no specific prescriptions have been formulated. However, in literature several work focus on both the evaluation of the cognitive safety of such human-robot interaction (e.g. [2], [3], [4]) and the development of technical measures to mitigate the stress/cognitive workload associated to such human-robot interaction (e.g. [5]). However, to the best of the project's participants, there is a lack of integration between the mechanical and the psychological safety. In fact, there are no works that

² The Research Ethics Committee cannot give its opinion on research projects within the scope of which data have already been collected through the procedure under analysis.

On the other hand, it is possible to request an ethical opinion from the Committee regarding projects initiated in the past, within which only now research activities have intervened for which ethical investigation is necessary.

consider both the problems of mechanical and psychological safety at the same time. The goal of such project is the one of developing and validating a method which aims at enhancing productivity, mechanical and cognitive safety of such collaborative workstation.

2.4.2 General aims, specific objectives and expected results (max 200 words)

As mentioned in the previous section, the goal of such project is the one of developing and validating a method which aims at enhancing productivity, mechanical and cognitive safety of such collaborative workstation. In particular, the principle that is implemented is explained in the following lines. The fundamental assumption is the following one: when the human operator is observing the robot or has the robot in its field of view, he is more aware of the robot's actions with respects to the moments in which the robot is not in its field of view. The developed method, then increases the speed of the manipulator up to a maximum value as the robot gets closer to the point where the human is looking at (i.e. as the awareness of the human of the robot's operations increases). The scaling of the manipulator's speed, then, is performed considering both the awareness of the human (safety with respect to collisions) and its cognitive load (psychological safety). The expected results is that the collaboration achieved by deploying such method will be more productive and safer, both mechanically and psychologically.

2.4.3 Is the research conducted with volunteers, , for the purpose of evaluating the safety and/or effectiveness of techniques/devices/treatments aimed at improving their well-being?

YES

NO

2.4.4 Methods of survey and processing of collected data:

To collect data questionnaires, biometric data (eye-gaze, i.e. the point where the human is looking at, heart rate, electrical dermal activity) and video recordings are exploited (no audio).

2.4.5 Numerosity and possible stratification of the sample

Test are performed with a number of people no larger than 45.

2.4.6 Description of the experimental procedure (attach any examples of the material and stimuli used)

The experimental procedure is structured as follows (only one participant at a time will execute the test):

STEP 1: The participant will sign the privacy information form. On the information form the participants have to indicate name and surname, e-mail, date and place of birth. This data will only be asked for the privacy information form and will not appear on the questionnaires the participants have to fill out in the next steps.

STEP 2: The participant will complete a questionnaire where they will indicate the following personal data: Age, Gender. They will also have to answer some questions about their attitude to robot using. There are no open questions, participants will have to answer indicating a point range (for example they will read this statement "I would feel uneasy if robots really had emotions" and answer using a five-point scale: 1 = I disagree to 5 = I agree).

STEP 3: The tester will execute an assembly of a product by collaborating with a cobot (collaborative robot). This task will be videorecorded. And during the task the participants eye-gaze, pupil size, heart rate, electrical dermal activity will be registered to measure the stress-level of the operator.

STEP 4: After fulfilling the task, the participant will be given a second questionnaire. Also in this phase there will be no open questions, participants will have to answer indicating a point range. No personal data will be collected through this questionnaire.

After each session, the collected data will be tagged with session indicators (e.g., first session, second session, etc.) as a security measure for data protection. This tagging system ensures that the researcher can accurately associate data from the questionnaire, video, eye-gaze, pupil size, and heart rate with a single participant, without marking them with direct indicators of the participants identity.

2.4.7 Bibliography (max. 15)

- [1]: Gualtieri L, Rauch E, Vidoni R; Emerging research fields in safety and ergonomics in industrial collaborative robotics: A systematic literature review; *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 2021
- [2]: Panchetti T, Pietrantoni L, Puzzo G, Gualtieri L, Fraboni F; Assessing the relationship between cognitive workload, workstation design, user acceptance and trust in collaborative robotics; *Applied Sciences*, 2023
- [3]: Lagomarsino M, Lorenzini M, Balatti P, De Momi E, Ajoudani A; Pick the right co-worker: online assessment of cognitive ergonomics in human-robot collaborative assembly; *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and Developmental Systems*, 2022
- [4]: Lagomarsino M, Lorenzini M, De Momi E, Ajoudani A; An online framework for cognitive load assessment in industrial tasks; *Robotics and Computer-integrated Manufacturing*, 2022
- [5]: Lagomarsino M, Lorenzini M, De Momi E, Ajoudani A; Robot trajectory adaptation to optimize trade-off between human cognitive ergonomics and workplace productivity in collaborative tasks; *IEEE IROS*, 2022

SECTION 3 – DETAILS RELATED TO THE PARTICIPANTS

3.1 What categories of individuals will take part in the study?

- Students of the Free University of Bozen/Bolzano
- Adults able to express their consent

3.2 Is it possible that some of the potential participant(s) may be in a relationship with the researcher such that consent to participation may not be entirely free of pressure (e.g., student-pupil/teacher, student-student/professor-professor, minor/educator-teacher, patient/physician, employee or worker-employer-employer)?

- YES
 NO

If YES, please indicate how you intend to minimize the possibility of the person feeling obliged to take part in the research.

If a participant has a personal relationship/direct knowledge with one of the researchers involved in the project, that researcher will not be part of the people which will execute the experimental test. Immediately after the test, data will be anonymized, thus making it impossible to trace back the experimental performance to the name of a person. The video recordings will be analyzed only by researchers which had no knowledge with the participant. If a person states that he does not want to be recorded, the recording won't be performed.

3.3 Characteristics of the study participant(s).

3.3.1 Inclusion criteria (specify)

Adults (age greater than 18).

3.3.2 Exclusion criteria (specify)

Being younger than 18.

3.4 How will participants be recruited?

Word of mouth and direct personal invitation (mailing list to general groups will NOT be used).

- **Attachment 3.4.1:** Copies of materials used to recruit participants (posters, fliers, messages posted on the web, etc.).

3.5 Are there expected to be material benefits for those taking part in the research, including any reimbursement of expenses?

- YES
 NO

Freie Universität Bozen
Libera Università di Bolzano
Università Lìedia de Bulsan

Comitato Etico della Ricerca
Beirat für die Ethik in der Forschung
Research Ethics Committee

If YES, which ones and under what conditions?

.....
.....

SECTION 4 - SURVEY TOOLS, RISK, AND RISK MANAGEMENT

4.1 The research involves (indicate all appropriate items and attach copies of the tools used; where this is not possible, indicate the topics that will be covered)

- questionnaires
- Observation of the behaviour of unaware participants
- audio and/or video recordings of participants
- recording of eye movements
- recording of behavioural responses, opinions or judgments
- measurement of physiological parameters (e.g., heart rate, etc.)

- **Attachment 4.1:** Copies of material relevant to the research (questionnaires, list of questions asked in the interviews, examples of visual stimuli, etc.) ³

4.2 Could the procedure expose the participant(s) to psychological, social, or physical risks? If YES, please describe the nature of these risks and the preventive interventions put in place to minimize possible consequences (min 500, max 1000 words).

With respect to psychological risks, the participant is not exposed to them. In fact, the human-robot collaboration exploiting industrial collaborative robots has become, nowadays, a common practice in industrial scenarios, and it can be considered as one of the usual industrial scenarios. With respect to social risks, the participant is not exposed to them. In fact, the experiment is executed by one participant at a time (nobody except the present researchers could know their identity) and the video recording is analyzed only by the researchers that do not have a personal knowledge/relationship with the participant. With respect to physical risks, to the best of the authors knowledge, the only possible risk is the one of a collision with the robot. Such risk is mitigated by the following actions:

- The robot deployed in the experiment is a certified collaborative robot (UR5e, produced by Universal Robots), which is characterized by a lower weight with respect to an industrial robot. The severity of a possible collision is then mitigated by the relative low inertias associated with the reduced weight of such robot.
- The participant will have at its disposal an emergency button to immediately stop the robot (which can also be used if the participant wants to interrupt the experiment for whatever reason). Such button removes power to the robot and engages the mechanical brakes which cause a stop of the robot motions.
- another stop button will be provided to the researcher (or a research confederate) in case a user starts panicking and is not capable of activating the safety measure.

³ In case the material is developed incrementally during the research, the Committee may give prior approval provided that the researcher submits the gradually developed tools prior to their use by request for supplementation, with reference to the approval code already assigned.

4.3 Does the research foresee participants being misled, i.e. not being provided with relevant information prior to obtaining consent to participate?

YES

NO

If YES, describe what information is omitted, justify why, and indicate when and how participants will be informed of the deception. (min 500, max 1000 words).

.....
.....

4.4 Is it possible that the study puts researchers in potentially dangerous situations from a psychological, physical, legal point of view?

YES

NO

If YES, please describe the nature of the risk and the measures taken to protect the safety of the researcher(s). (min 500 words)

.....

4.5 Is there a risk that the results of the study could be dual-use, i.e. could also be used for military purposes?

YES

NO

If YES, please specify:

.....
.....

SECTION 5 - INFORMATION AND CONSENT RELATED TO THE PROJECT

5.1 How will participants be informed about the study and the procedures they will undergo?

Participants will be informed about the study and the procedures they will undergo with the file reported as Attachment 5.1. Such document describes the procedure of the experiment as well as the right of the participants to interrupt the experiment whenever he wants and of the procedure to follow if he would like to delete his personal data retrieve during the experiment. Once he has read the document, the researcher will be available to answer possible questions of the participant.

- **Attachment 5.1:** Information document

5.2 How will consent to participate in the Project be acquired and documented?

Consent to participate to the project is acquired exploiting a paper form, which will be signed by the participants (Attachment 5.2.1).

- **Attachment 5.2.1:** consent module
- **Attachment 5.2.2:** consent module (minors) – *NOT REQUIRED (only adults will take part in the experiment)*

5.3 Taking into account that information must be given to all/potential participants, what arrangements will be made to inform those who cannot give consent (e.g., minors) and to acquire their "consent"?⁴

The people who cannot give consent are automatically excluded from the experiments.

- **Attachment 5.3.1:** Information document for consent : *NOT REQUIRED (only people capable of giving their consent will take part in the experiment)*
- **Attachment 5.3.2:** module for consent: *NOT REQUIRED (only people capable of giving their consent will take part in the experiment)*

5.4 How will the results of the research be made public?

The results of the research, if they will be considered relevant from a scientific point of view, once they will be anonymized and statistically elaborated, they will be published in scientific papers.

5.5 Will the participants be informed about the results of the research?

YES

⁴ In the case of research with minors, it is recommended that in the case of data collection, the willingness of the minor to participate should be verified, in addition to the consent required from the parent/legal guardian.

NO

If YES, when and how?

If allowed by the license policies of the Journals/Conference where papers might be published, a digital version of the paper or a link to the paper will be published in the website of the Smart Mini Factory.

5.6 Is there a possibility that during the research, regardless of the objectives of the study, information regarding the psycho-physical condition of the participants might emerge?

YES

NO

If YES, please indicate how this data will be processed.

.....
.....

SECTION 6 – PERSONAL DATA TREATMENT

6.1 Will personal data be processed as part of the project?⁵

- YES**
 NO

If YES, select the type of data processed.

- Anonymous data⁶
- Personal data
- Special Categories of Data (Sensitive Data)
- Genetic data
 - Biometric data
 - Health related data
 - Data related to Sexual life or sexual orientation
 - Data related to Ethnicity
 - Data related to political opinion
 - Data related to union affiliation
 - Data related to religious or philosophical beliefs
 - Data related to criminal record

6.2 The project was submitted for privacy analysis

- YES**
 NO

If YES, please attach the privacy analysis form (GDPR questionnaire), completed and signed.

- **Attachment 6.1:** Privacy analysis in digitally signed pdf format.

⁵ Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ("data subject"); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or to one or more characteristic features of that natural person's physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

⁶ Pay attention to the difference between anonymous data and pseudonymized data. Pseudonymization is the processing of personal data in such a way that it can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is stored separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that such personal data is not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art.4, no. 5 EU Reg. 2016/679 - GDPR).

Anonymous data (information that does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or personal data anonymized in such a way that the data subject is not or is no longer identifiable) are not treated as personal data. Pseudonymized data are not anonymous data, as they always allow for some form of reidentification.

STATEMENT OF RESPONSIBILITY

I, the undersigned **VIDONI RENATO**.....

responsible for the project: **HUMAN ROBOT ADAPTIVE COLLABORATION**.....

.....

.....

.....

DECLARE

That the information in this document is accurate,

AND I COMMIT MYSELF TO

- a. give written notice of the start and end date of the project, as well as of any early suspension of the project with reasons;
- b. conduct the project in the manner indicated;
- c. not to introduce forms of incentives for participation that could restrict freedom or autonomy in decision-making and expression of consent;
- d. to inform in writing of adverse events that occurred during the course of the study and of any factors that might affect the safety of participants or the continuation of the study;
- e. not introduce changes to the protocol without a favorable opinion from the Research Ethics Committee;
- f. to inform the Research Ethics Committee of any change in the composition of the research team, either in the case of termination of the collaboration of one or more members or in the case of inclusion of new members;
- g. comply with any recommendations requested by the Research Ethics Committee.

Date **21/12/2023**.....

Signature of the project leader

#5

COMPLETE

Collector: ENG_SestoSenso_MManzardo (Email)
Started: Thursday, October 26, 2023 8:46:47 AM
Last Modified: Monday, December 11, 2023 5:05:01 PM
Time Spent: Over a month

Page 1: General Aspects of the Project

Q1

Project title

HUMAN-ROBOT ADAPTIVE COLLABORATION

Q2

Contact details

name of the editor	Luca Gultieri
institutional email address	luca.gultieri@unibz.it
phone number	+39 3396509833

Q3

Duration of the Project

expected start date of the project (DD/MM/AAAA)	27/12/2023
expected start date of data collection (DD/MM/AAAA)	27/12/2023
expected duration in months	4,5

Q4

Description of the project (max. 500 characters) Please describe in simple terms the research project: please focus on the methodologies, the procedure and the objectives, trying to be as clear and concise as possible.

The project has the goal to investigate human-robot interaction within working context.

The participants will be asked to perform tasks with a collaborative robot (industrial robot that can safely operate alongside humans in a shared workspace).

The proposed method allows humans to regulate the robot's speed by utilizing data derived from the point where they are looking, known as the eye's gaze point. The method is based on the following assumption: when the operator is observing the robot / has the robot in its field of view, he/she is generally more aware of the robot's actions with respect to the moments in which the robot is out of the field of view of the operator. The developed method increases the speed of the robot, within a maximum limit speed, as the attention of the operator increases (e.g. when the observation point of the human gets closer to the robot).

The tests are structured in the following way (only one participant at a time will execute the test):

STEP 1: The participant will sign the privacy information form. On the information form the participants have to indicate name and surname, e-mail, date and place of birth. This data will only be asked for the privacy information form and will not appear on the questionnaires the participants have to fill out in the next steps.

STEP 2: The participant will complete a questionnaire where they will indicate the following personal data: Age, Gender and Session indicators (pseudonymised data). They will also have to answer some questions about their attitude to robot using. There are no open questions, participants will have to answer indicating a point range (for example they will read this statement "I would feel uneasy if robots really had emotions" and answer using a five-point scale: 1 = I disagree to 5 = I agree).

STEP 3: The tester will execute an assembly of a product by collaborating with a cobot (collaborative robot). This task will be videorecorded. And during the task the participants eye-gaze, pupil size, heart rate, electrical dermal activity will be registered to measure the stress-level of the operator.

STEP 4: After fulfilling the task, the participant will be given a second questionnaire. Also in this phase there will be no open questions, participants will have to answer indicating a point range. No personal data will be collected through this questionnaire.

After each session, the collected data will be tagged with session indicators (e.g., first session, second session, etc.) as a security measure for data protection. This tagging system ensures that the researcher can accurately associate data from the questionnaire, video, eye-gaze, pupil size, and heart rate with a single participant, without marking them with direct indicators of the participants identity.

The overall purpose of the project is to understand how well the human-robot collaboration works in terms of efficiency and quality of the collaboration and whether the proposed method of adjusting robot speed based on the operator's attention is effective.

Q5 questionnaire in paper form,

Method of data acquisition Please describe briefly how do you intend to collect data. Please note that the question refers to all types of data collected in the research project, not only to personal data.

observation,
measurement of physiological parameters (e.g. heart rate, etc.)

,
other (please specify):

Video recording (and no audio), Eye-tracking

Q6
In case of audio or audio and video recordings, please specify WHICH activities will be recorded.

There is only video-recording of the assembly activities/collaboration with the robot to be performed in a lab environment.

Q7 anonymous data

Dissemination of the project results

Q8
Who is the project leader? Please specify and describe its role.

Prof. Vidoni Renato

Q9
Are there any other entities/institutions involved in the project? If yes, please specify and describe their role.

University of Bologna (Research Unit on Human Factors, Risk and Safety), Department of Psychology. Supports the research team in the experimental design. University of Bologna only processes anonymised data.

Q10
Persons involved in the research project format: surname first name (role, unibz/external) e.g. "Rossi Mario (RTD, unibz)"

principal investigator

Vidoni Renato (Full Professor, unibz)

project team

Gualtieri Luca (RTD, unibz), Manzardo Matteo (PhD student), colleagues from Bologna

Q11 Yes (if so, a separate application should be submitted to researchethics@unibz.it once the privacy analysis has been successfully completed)

Will you submit the research project to the Research Ethics Committee?

Q12

Where does the research project take place?

Smart Mini Factory Lab, FIRST Lab of Unibz

Q13

Yes

Does your research involve personal data collection and/or processing? Personal data are any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. ATTENTION: anonymous data (information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable) is not treated as personal data. Pseudonymized data are not anonymous data as they always allow some form of re-identification.

Page 2: Participants Engagement

Q14

Who will take part in the studies? Please describe and specify the category (e.g. students of first and second class of high school, adults working in the social area, etc..).

adults: **Students of BSc or MSc unibz (older than 18), unibz researchers and PhD students, volunteers (workers from factories)**

Q15

Expected number of participants

maximum 40

Q16

How will the information and invitation to participate in the research be disseminated? Please flag and specify.

other: **personal invitation (word of mouth)**

Q17

Shall the option to give one's consent to data processing not be entirely free (e.g. student/professor, patient/doctor, majority/minority relationships), please indicate what precautions are being taken to minimise the possibility that the subject may feel obliged to take part in the research.

The experimental procedure is explained at the beginning with a particular emphasis on the fact that participants can stop the experiment in any moment without providing explanations about their decisions. This is also specified in the illustrative sheet given to the participants at the beginning of the experiment. Data subjects have the right to withdraw their consent at any time by contacting privacy@unibz.it, as described in the privacy policy.

Q18

Please attach a copy of the material used (e.g. questionnaire, interview schedules,..)

RichiestaIniziale_EyeTracking_18.10.23_revLG_revFF%20copia.docx (41.8KB)

Q19

Here you can upload further material used

MicrosoftTeams-image.png (191.9KB)

Q20

Respondent skipped this question

Here you can upload further material used

Page 3: Personal Data Processing

Q21

Controller

Please identify Unibz Role Controller (natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data) - in the case of a project that is carried out solely by unibz, this last is Controller Joint Controller (two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing the same personal data) Processor (natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller)

Q22

Please attach contract/agreement with other institutions/subjects involved in the research

Grant%20Agreement-101070310-Sestosenso.pdf (9.1MB)

Q23

Categories of personal data processed Please specify and describe more in detail which categories of personal data are processed in the project. genetic data: personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question; biometric data: personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data

common (e.g. name and surname, e-mail-address, phone number, age,...)

data ex art. 9 GDPR: biometric data

data ex art. 9 GDPR: data concerning health

name and surname, e-mail, date and place of birth - for Information form; Age, Gender - questionnaire; Image

Eye-tracking (pupil dilation, eye movement)

Heart Rate, Electrical dermal activity (which measures the stress-level of the operator).

Q24

Processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures (data ex art. 10 GDPR) shall be carried out only under the control of official authority or when the processing is authorised by Union or Member State law

not applicable

Q25

Retention period of personal data Please note: personal data may only be kept for no longer than strictly necessary for the specific purpose; when personal data are anonymised, they are no longer personal data.

4 months. Within that period data will be anonymized by permanently deleting any reference/association between the personal data and the results of the experiment, without allowing to trace the data back to the person from which they were retrieved. Moreover, data will be statistically elaborated, thus making it impossible to associate the aggregated data to a person. After the 4 months data will be permanently deleted. 4 months is the amount of time considered as the minimum necessary to process them (according to the researchers involved in the project).

Q26

As specified in the privacy information sheet that will be provided to participants, data may be processed only for carrying out the indicated research project. Do you intend to use the data also for other purposes or other research projects?

No

Q27

Are the personal data collected adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (data minimization)? Please indicate the reason why data collection is necessary (e.g. "e-mail address and phone number are necessary in order to allow communication between researchers and participants/to arrange appointments",...) and describe any additional minimization measures adopted ("date of birth is replaced with age group",...)

Eye-tracking (pupil, eye gaze), Heart Rate, electrical dermal activity and age are necessary to assess the effectiveness of the human-robot collaboration and are required to accomplish the goals of the research project, while the anagraphical data are required to sign the Privacy form.

Q28**invitation for the user to check**

What measures are taken to ensure that personal data is accurate and up-to-date?

Q29

Unibz is certified ISO 27001. Are there any other standards applicable to the personal data processing? (e.g. code of conduct, certification, professional code of conduct, code of conduct for a certain research field, etc.)

Yes (please specify)::

"code of conduct", "Regole deontologiche per trattamenti a fini statistici o di ricerca scientifica pubblicate ai sensi dell'art. 20, comma 4, del d.lgs. 10 agosto 2018, n. 101 - 19 dicembre 2018"

Q30

How will the privacy information be distributed and collected?

in paper form. The research team will collect the signed forms directly from the participants.**Q31**

Interested parties participating in the Research Project for statistical or scientific research purposes are required to provide their consent for the processing of data ex art. 9 and 10 GDPR. How do you intend to collect these consents? Please specify the ways in which the subjects (natural persons concerned) participating in the Research Project will be able to express their consent in a free, specific, informed and unequivocal manner

if applicable, specify: :

Paper form.

Q32

For data processing based on the data subject's consent pursuant to Art. 9, will you be able to prove that the data subject has given his/her consent to the processing of his/her personal data for statistical or scientific research purposes? Please remember to keep track of the information provided to the data subject and to keep the acquisition of consent for three years

yes

Q33

Please attach a copy of the privacy information for participants Please remember to use UNIBZ templates.

UNIBZ%20DOC_G_informativa%20liberatoria%20adulti_audio%20video_categoria%20particolare%20dati%20it-de_def.pdf (252KB)

Q34

Respondent skipped this question

Here you can upload further privacy information sheets.

Q35

Respondent skipped this question

Here you can upload further privacy information sheets.

Q36

Where and how the project data will be stored?Please note: the question refers to all data stored in the research project, not only personal data.

In an Office Driver, accessible only by the members of the unibz's research team of the experiment. The paper form documents will be stored in a locked cabinet in unibz accessible only by the researchers involved in the project.

Q37

Which unibz software or ICT-tools are used for personal data processing?Please remember that anonymous data is not personal data, e.g. if you process only statistical data with a tool, you don't need to specify.

Microsoft Office Suite (Teams, Outlook, Excel, Power point, Word, OneNote, OneDrive..)

,

Matlab,

Ansys, ESRI ArcGIS, IBM SPSS+Amos, JetBrains, Keyhot, MaxQDA, Maple, MSC Adams+Easy5, RhinoCam, Sigmaplot, SAS, Solid Works, Stata and/or Wanda

,

Other (please specify):

For the data processing of the research project, tools from the company Microsoft are used. All tools used by unibz are subjected to a risk assessment according to ISO 27001 before purchase. Microsoft offers customers the EU Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC) (also known as EU Model Clauses) that provide specific guarantees around transfers of personal data for in-scope services. The EU Model Clauses are used in agreements between service providers (such as Microsoft) and their customers to ensure that any personal data leaving the EEA will be transferred in compliance with the GDPR. The use of Microsoft tools always entails an international data transfer to the US-countries. The Microsoft Corporation is part of the DataProtection Framework.

Q38

What are the unibz data supporting assets? Please select assets on which personal data rely.

device (e.g. camera, voice recorder, ..),
cloud,
body function sensors (temperature, humidity, heartbeat, ...)
,
paper documents,
other (please specify)::
Eye-tracking

Q39

Which NON unibz software or ICT-tools are used for personal data processing? List hardware, software and other tools used in the project and the reasons for using instruments not unibz

Python <https://www.python.org/privacy/>

Python is a programming language (not a software) used by the research team to create an interface that enables communication between different devices, such as eye-tracker and unibz computer. Attached to this questionnaire (Q19) you can find a picture of the data cycle: the whole cycle is closed, runs on unibz tools and is not connected to our network. It is important to note that although the image shows a MacBook, the research team will be using a unibz notebook.

As a programming language, Python does not involve the input of personal data for its functioning. In other words, the Python tool does not handle any personal data.

Q40

What are the NON unibz data supporting assets? Please select assets on which personal data rely.

other (please specify)::
EDA (Electrical dermal activity and heart rate)

Page 4: DPIA and DTIA filter

Q41

DPIA is required where 1 or more criteria are met

Innovative use or applying new technological or organisational solutions (e.g. eyetracking glasses, body sensors,..)

Q42

If you answered "Controller has done a DPIA for this project" at the previous question, please attach the relevant DPIA.

Respondent skipped this question

Q43

No

DTIA filter Will data be transferred to countries outside the European Economic Area EEA (EU+ Norway, Liechtenstein, Iceland) or to international organizations? Please note that DTIAs for transfers through IT-tools are centrally managed.

Page 5: DPIA (Process)

Q44

The DPIA document is edited by (who provides data to complete the DPIA document):

Renato Vidoni, Luca Gualtieri, Mateo Manzardo

Q45

unibz Privacy Team

The DPIA document is reviewed by:

Q46

**President of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano as
Legal Representative**

The DPIA document is validated by:

Q47

What is the processing under consideration? Please specify if the analysis covers the full project or only a part of the project.

The analysis covers the whole project.

Q48

What are the responsibilities linked to the personal data processing? Please describe the responsibilities of the subjects involved - who is responsible for what?

The Principal investigator together with the Research team are responsible for the correct management of personal data. All researchers and the principal investigator are unibz employees who are duly authorised to process personal data as part of their work assignment.

Q49

Please flag the phases of the life cycle of personal data in the project covered in this analysis.

collection of data,
storage,
utilization,
sharing,
archiving,
anonymization,
deletion

Q50

Collection Phase

How do you collect personal data and which measurements/precautions are adopted to guarantee security and protection for data subjects? e.g. "data are collected via questionnaires in paper format" ("HOW") ... and the seats of participants will be arranged in such a way that they cannot see each others answers" ("measurements/precautions").

The data will be collected in paper forms and using the devices EDA, eye-tracking, heart rate measurement system.

Eye tracking device transmits data directly to the computer (then they will be uploaded in the unibz's protected driver and, once uploaded, they will be permanently deleted by the computer), while for EDA and heart rate data, they are transferred to the computer through an external storage device (USB). Once transferred to the driver, the data will be permanently deleted from the temporary storage. The participants will execute the experiment one at a time.

Q51

Storage PhaseHow do you store personal data during the various steps/phases of the research project and which measurements/precautions are adopted to guarantee security and protection for data subjects? e.g. "Paper documents are stored in a locked cabinet in the office of the P.I. accessible only to authorized persons", "data is stored on unibz notebook protected by a secure password", "data is stored on unibz servers", etc.

The data collected using the devices EDA, eye-tracking (pupil dilation, eye movement), heart rate measurement system and videos will be digitally stored on OneDrive to which only the research team has access.

Paper documents are stored in a locked cabinet accessible only the research team has access.

Q52

Utilization PhaseHow do you use personal data collected in the research project and which measurements/precautions are adopted to guarantee security and protection for data subjects?

In the utilization phase data will be elaborated statistically (thus making them anonymous after the processing) exploiting unibz tool Matlab and programming language Python.

Q53

Sharing Phase How do you share personal data between subjects involved in the research project and which measurements/precautions are adopted to guarantee security and protection for data subjects?

Data will be accessible to the research team through the driver (OneDrive) provided by the University of Bolzano which will be made accessible only to the authorized researchers.

Only the results of the statistical analysis, derived from already anonymized data, will be possibly published.

Q54

Archiving Phase How do you archive personal data after use and which measurements/precautions are adopted to guarantee security and protection for data subjects?

Data are stored exploiting the driver provided by the University of Bolzano which will be made accessible only by the authorized researchers. The paper forms will be stored in a locked cabinet accessible only by the researchers involved in the experiment.

Q55

Anonymizing Phase Please describe how this phase is carried on and in particular the features that grant anonymity, diversity and un-closeness for data subjects.

Once statistically elaborated and, consequently, anonymized, original data will be deleted and only the results of the statistical analysis will be published (in this form data are completely anonymous). Data which cannot be anonymized (e.g. videos) will be permanently deleted.

Q56

Deletion Phase Please describe how this phase is carried on as well as the features that grant security and protection for data subjects, considering also deletion by external subjects and data by researchers.

Once statistically elaborated, original data will be permanently deleted. With respect to paper forms, once the project will be completed, they will be destroyed with a paper shredder.

Q57

How can data subjects exercise their rights concerning personal data?

other or not applicable (please specify the modalities to exercise the indicated rights or the reason why the rights are not applicable):
by contacting the research team (see contact data on the privacy information sheet)

Q58

Yes

Are Unibz ICT tools used? If you use devices and/or tools provided by unibz, the following measures are always applied: - application of the anti malware measures defined by ICT unibz (e.g. antivirus, firewall, regular updates,...) - Unibz is certified ISO 27001 - Servers of unibz are protected with sophisticated security measures - Backup system is in place - Unibz has appointed the Data Protection Officer (DPO) - Unibz has a data breach policy - regular updates of UNIBZ privacy policies - authorization system - logical access control

Q59

Measures applied for devices and processing not under unibz control. If instruments are not under unibz ICT control and process is not governed by unibz, researchers have to grant security autonomously using some of the following measures (please flag the measures adopted):

automatic screen locking,
 website security,
 physical access control,
 anti-malware (antivirus, malware detection, vulnerability scanning, ...)
 ,
 maintainance

Q60

Analytical description of security measures autonomously adopted. Please describe security measures regarding paper document security, physical access control, secure communication precautions, ...

Protection with anti-malware, password, physical control of the device, maintenance, automatic screen locking.

Q61

What are the main risk sources?

external online attack (hacking, virus, security attack, malware)
 ,
 physical intrusion by unauthorized persons (e.g. forcing doors)
 ,
 data left unlocked in accessible area (e.g. device left unattended when logged into an account, documents left on shared photocopiers)
 ,
 accidental or incidental misuse by employees/collaborators (e.g. emails being sent to wrong recipient)
 ,
 disloyal or negligent employees/collaborators,
 inappropriate access controls (e.g. insecure password)

Q62

Other risk sources:

To the best of the knowledge of the members of the research team, there are no other main sources of risk.

Q63

Risk Assessment loss of confidentiality (disclosure of data) Determine the severity/level of risk for data subject's right and freedoms Risk is:- high: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is over 5;- medium: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is between 2 and 4;- low: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is 1.

medium impact (2)

low likelihood (1)

Q64

Risk Assessment loss of integrity (modification of data) Determine the severity/level of risk for data subject's right and freedoms Risk is:- high: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is over 5;- medium: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is between 2 and 4;- low: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is 1.

low impact (1)

low likelihood (1)

Q65

Risk Assessment loss of availability of data (without unauthorised access by third parties) Determine the severity/level of risk for data subject's right and freedoms Risk is:- high: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is over 5;- medium: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is between 2 and 4;- low: if the result of multiplying of impact by likelihood is 1.

low impact (1)

low likelihood (1)

Q66

medium

Considering the results of risk assessments in Q77-78-79, the total risk is defined as:

Q67

Please explain reasons for your risk evaluation. Suppose, for example, that in your project video-recorded interviews with minors are conducted: a possible answer could be " ..The loss of confidentiality and integrity of the video recordings could have a high psychological, emotional or reputational impact, as they contain very personal and sensitive information and maybe also embarrassing declarations. However, the likelihood of a loss is very low, as the video recordings are saved in password-protected files on UNIBZ servers and are accessible only by the research team. All security measures recommended by ICT UNIBZ are applied. Also, recordings will be deleted immediately after transcription (within max. 2 weeks) and transcriptions are anonymized by deleting all information which could allow identification of participants ...". PLEASE NOTE THIS IS ONLY AN EXAMPLE FOR CLARIFICATION PURPOSES.

A potential loss of confidentiality, integrity and availability could potentially cause a potential risk for the data subjects since it could lead to the exposure of health related data.

Even though there is a potential risk for the data subject in case of a data breach, the researcher adopts a large number of security measures which contribute to concretely reduce and minimize the risk:

- Data is stored on unibz devices, protected by regularly updated password and by double authentication as is standard practice for unibz ICT systems.
- Only Unibz ICT tools are used, which are ISO 27001 certified and guarantee a high level of security. Anti malware measures are adopted, servers are password protected, logical access control systems are provided, backup systems are installed, regular updates are made.
- Only data necessary for research activities or to certify the granting of consent are collected and stored no longer as necessary to fulfill the research purpose.
- The researchers are informed about the roles and responsibilities regarding personal data processing.
- Unibz also has an internal procedure for data breach management. Loss of confidentiality, considering the measures taken, has a low likelihood to happen and a medium severity. In fact, physical data are present, but no data regarding illnesses are retrieved/stored. The loss of integrity and the loss of availability affects the quality of the research, but does not affect the participant, thus having a low impact.

Q68

Which additional security measures can contribute to reduce risk for data subject's right and freedoms? These measures are indispensable in the case of HIGH risk. In other cases they are optional.

To the best of the knowledge of the members of the research team, no other additional security measures must be taken.

Page 7: DTIA (Personal data transfer)

Q69

To which country the data will be transferred?

Other (please specify):

USA

Q70

Is the transfer managed centrally by Unibz (ICT Tools, ...)

No

Page 8: DTIA (Legitimacy of Transfer)

Q71 Respondent skipped this question

Data transfer Lawfulness

Q72 Respondent skipped this question

If Data Transfer based on SCC or BCR, please upload document

Page 9: Privacy DTIA (Derogations)

Q73 None of the above

Derogations for specific situations pursuant to art. 49 GDPR?

Page 10: Privacy DTIA (3)

Q74 Respondent skipped this question

Technical measures to ensure an adequate level of protection: Data storage that do not require access to data in the clear (e.g. use of a hosting service provider in a third country to store personal data for backup purposes) under the following conditions: strong encryption, state of the art (key length, operative mode), time period related to strength of the encryption, SW for encryption verified and maintained, proper managing of the keys, keys under control of the exporter

Q75 Respondent skipped this question

Technical measures to ensure an adequate level of protection: Transfer of pseudonymized data (e.g. pseudonymisation before transfer to a third country for analysis, e.g., for purposes of research) under the following conditions: data can't be related to data subject without additional information, additional information are under control of exporter, only exporter has control of algorithm or repository for re-identification, no other data base can be used to re-identifying data.

Q76

Respondent skipped this question

Technical measures to ensure an adequate level of protection: Encrypted data merely transiting (e.g. data transfer to a country with an adequate protection - data is only routed via a third country) under the following conditions: geographically routed, encryption protocols effective/state of the art, decryption is possible only outside third country, trustworthy public key certification authority or infrastructure, updated measures for active and passive attacks, encryption on application level if transport encryption is not sufficient, strength of encryption is related to specific time of confidentiality, SW for encryption verified and maintained, no backdoors, well managed process for keys.

Q77

Respondent skipped this question

Technical measures to ensure an adequate level of protection: Protected Recipient under the following conditions: the law protects recipient from public authorities requests, the protection extends to all data in possession by data importer, the importer doesn't use a processor sensitive to public authorities requests, data are encrypted before to be transmitted, key for decryption is under protected importer control, correspondence encryption/decryption key.

Q78

Respondent skipped this question

Technical measures to ensure an adequate level of protection: Split or multi-party processing under the following conditions: information is split into two or more parts, each part is processed by a processor in different third country, the processing is possible only when processor has all the splitted parts of the message, algorithm used is secure, no evidence of collaboration between different authorities of different third country, no attribution to specific data subject can be made.

Q79

Respondent skipped this question

Additional contractual measures (Difficult to impose legal obligation to Public authorities (Third party) these can only determine a general awareness or impose recipient to adopt some technical measure and should be combined with other technical and organisational measures to provide the level of data protection required.)

Q80

Respondent skipped this question

Additional contractual measures: Transparency obligation
Exporter imposes the data recipient contractually:

Q81

Respondent skipped this question

Additional contractual measures: Obligations for recipient to take specific actions

Q82

Respondent skipped this question

Additional contractual measures: Empowering data subjects to exercise their rights

Page 11: Declaration

Q83

The Principal Investigator hereby declares under his/her full responsibility:

that the answers given above are complete, accurate and true

,

to report any future relevant changes to the information provided

Q84

Ok, I have read and understood this information.

Please note: If you intend to submit the research project to the Ethics Committee for approval, you need to send a separate request to the Ethics Committee after the conclusion (approval) of this privacy analysis.

Page 12: Attachments

Q85

Respondent skipped this question

Attachment 1

Q86

Respondent skipped this question

Attachment 2

Q87

Respondent skipped this question

Attachment 3

Q88

Respondent skipped this question

Attachment 4

Page 13: Comments and Opinions

Q89

Respondent skipped this question

Further comments by Editor of the Questionnaire (if any)

Q90

Respondent skipped this question

Comments of the Privacy Team This field is reserved for the Privacy Team.

Q91

Respondent skipped this question

Where applicable: Are the obligations of data processors (different from unibz ICT Suppliers) clearly defined and governed by a contract? This question is answered by the Privacy Team.
